

Interstitial Lung Disease Associated with Chronic Nitrofurantoin Use

Erick Jafet González Roblero¹, Karla Fabiola Aguirre Avila², Erika Patricia Cerna Alcantar³, Elizabeth Arellano Pacheco⁴, Diana Karen Fernández López⁵, Hannia Sarali Mares Cárdenas⁶, Roberto Teutli Pérez⁷, Jesús Arturo Portillo Ibarra⁸, Mirtha Saavedra Vázquez⁹

^{1,2,3,4,5,6,7,8,9} General Hospital of Zone No 50, IMSS, San Luis Potosí, Mexico.

ABSTRACT

Introduction: Since 2011, nitrofurantoin has been reconsidered as a first-line treatment, but it can cause rare pulmonary and liver toxicity. Chronic use can lead to interstitial lung disease (ILD). The case presented highlights the suspicion of ILD in patients with respiratory symptoms after prolonged nitrofurantoin use.

Case presentation: A 64-year-old woman receiving nitrofurantoin long-term developed severe pulmonary symptoms. After ruling out infections and autoimmune diseases, pulmonary toxicity was suspected. Treatment produced significant improvement, and she was discharged, continuing therapy and discontinuing nitrofurantoin.

Conclusion: Nitrofurantoin toxicity is underreported in Mexico. Despite being safe, prolonged use can cause serious effects, so regular follow-up is essential.

KEYWORDS: Nitrofurantoin, Interstitial lung disease, Pulmonary fibrosis, Urinary tract infections, Adverse reaction to medications

ARTICLE DETAILS

Published On:
13 May 2025

Available on:
<https://ijmscrs.com/>

INTRODUCTION

Since 2011, nitrofurantoin has been reconsidered as a first-line treatment due to the increase in bacterial resistance to other antibiotics (1).

Although rare, the drug's package insert warns of possible pulmonary reactions and liver complications (1).

Nitrofurantoin-induced pulmonary toxicity was first reported in 1957, and since then, various clinical manifestations have been documented, ranging from acute to chronic forms (1). Acute forms are usually associated with hypersensitivity reactions, while chronic forms are linked to treatment duration, with most cases reported after more than six months of use. Among the latter is interstitial lung disease (ILD), a group of diffuse parenchymal diseases characterized by extensive alterations in alveolar and airway architecture, with similar clinical, radiographic, physiological, and pathological manifestations (2). Drug-induced ILD accounts for between 16% and 48% of nitrofurantoin-related adverse events documented in registry studies (3).

In this context, the clinical case we present highlights the importance of suspecting ILD in patients who develop respiratory symptoms after prolonged nitrofurantoin use.

CASE PRESENTATION

A 64-year-old female patient with no history of smoking or exposure to biomasses had a medical history of prediabetes under sitagliptin therapy and recurrent urinary tract infections, treated with nitrofurantoin 100 mg daily for the past 10 months without discontinuation.

Two months prior to her evaluation, she presented with cough, scant whitish sputum, mild dyspnea, and fatigue. She presented with worsening dyspnea, progressing to grade 4 on the mMRC dyspnea scale and oxygen saturation of 70%.

A chest X-ray revealed generalized bilateral pulmonary opacities and peribronchovascular interstitial thickening. Figure 1. A subsequent plain chest computed tomography (CT) scan showed bilateral ground-glass pulmonary opacities, thickening of the fissures, and thickening of the pleura. Figure 2.

Laboratory tests were obtained. See Table 1.

Due to the progressive deterioration of her clinical condition, she required hospitalization in the Intensive Care Unit (ICU), where she remained on noninvasive mechanical ventilation for 48 hours. Biochemical and microbiological studies were performed, including a respiratory viral panel,

Interstitial Lung Disease Associated with Chronic Nitrofurantoin Use

PPD, blood cultures, and bronchoalveolar lavage cultures, all with negative results.

Due to suspected autoimmune disease, antinuclear antibodies (ANAs) were ordered, reporting positivity (1:160, homogeneous pattern). Additional studies were performed (anti-double-stranded DNA, anti-SM, C-ANCA, P-ANCA, anti-Ro, anti-La, anti-Jo-1, anti-SCL-70 IgG, anti-cyclic citrullinated peptide IgG, and a panel of 11 myositis-specific antibodies), with negative results.

Due to deteriorating respiratory function and suspected pulmonary toxicity due to prolonged nitrofurantoin use, and after excluding other etiologies based on paraclinical results, 7 days after admission, treatment was initiated with pulses of methylprednisolone (250 mg IV every 8 hours for 7 days), mycophenolate mofetil (500 mg every 24 hours), rituximab (500 mg in a single dose), cyclophosphamide (400 mg in a single dose), and nintedanib (150 mg every 12 hours).

Clinical and radiological improvement was observed, with a progressive decrease in oxygen requirements, 5 days after starting treatment. Figure 3.

The patient was discharged with supplemental oxygen, steroids, mycophenolic acid, and nintedanib, in addition to the indefinite suspension of nitrofurantoin. Her laboratory results upon discharge are shown in Table 1.

Figure 1. Anteroposterior chest radiograph showing generalized bilateral pulmonary opacities and peribronchovascular interstitial thickening.

Figure 2. Plain chest computed tomography showed bilateral ground-glass opacities in the lungs, and thickened fissures and pleura. A. Axial section and B. Coronal section.

Figure 3. Plain chest computed tomography with radiological enhancement. A. Axial section and B. Coronal section.

Table 1. Laboratory results

	Admission	Upon discharge
Hemoglobin	13.8gr/dL	14.7 gr/dL
Hematocrit	40.8%	44.9%
Mean corpuscular volume	88.6 fL	87.7 fL
Mean Corpuscular Hemoglobin	29.9pg	28.7 pg
Leukocytes	7.9 K/uL	5.34 K/uL
Neutrophils	82%	4.9 k/uL
Lymphocytes	10%	0.19 k/uL
Monocytes	5%	0.15 k/uL
Eosinophils	2%	0.08 k/uL
Basophils	1%	0.0 k/uL
Platelets	223 mil k/uL	103 mil k/uL
Creatinine	0.8 mg/dL	0.49 mg/dL
Lactic dehydrogenase	435 U/L	
Glutamic-Oxaloacetic Transaminase	33 U/L	34 U/L
Glutamic Pyruvic Transaminase	26 U/L	10 U/L
Alkaline phosphatase	239 U/L	120 U/L
Albumin	2.6 g/dL	
D-dimer	0.15 mg/dl	
Serum sodium		139 mmol/L
Serum potassium		5.0 mmol/L
Serum chlorine		103 mmol/L
Serum calcium		9.2 mg/dL
C-reactive protein	0.037 mg/dl	

Interstitial Lung Disease Associated with Chronic Nitrofurantoin Use

DISCUSSION

Urinary tract infections (UTIs) are one of the most common bacterial infections worldwide, primarily affecting women (1). The microbial spectrum of cystitis and uncomplicated pyelonephritis is primarily composed of *Escherichia coli* (*E. coli*), representing between 75% and 95% of cases (4).

Nitrofurantoin belongs to the nitrofuran group and is activated by bacterial enzymes to a reduced form, which binds to bacterial ribosomes, inhibiting protein synthesis and affecting DNA, RNA, and bacterial cell wall synthesis (2). It is effective against a wide variety of Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria, including *E. coli* (1).

According to the latest edition of the Infectious Diseases Society of America (IDSA) guidelines for the treatment of uncomplicated cystitis and pyelonephritis (2010), nitrofurantoin (100 mg twice daily for five days) is an appropriate therapeutic option due to its low resistance rate and reduced risk of adverse effects. Its clinical efficacy is estimated to be 93%, while its microbiological efficacy is 88% (4).

The most common adverse effects include nausea and headache (4). Hypersensitivity reactions, such as rash, angioedema, asthma, fever, and arthralgia, have also been reported (1). However, the drug's package insert warns of possible pulmonary reactions and liver complications (1).

In a case series of women aged 50 to 95 years with recurrent urinary tract infections (UTIs), 9% developed lung disease associated with prolonged nitrofurantoin use (5).

Nitrofurantoin-induced pulmonary toxicity was first described in 1957, and since then, a wide spectrum of clinical manifestations has been documented, ranging from acute to chronic forms (1).

The estimated incidence of nitrofurantoin-induced lung injury is 1 in 5,000 acute and severe cases (2).

These pulmonary manifestations include interstitial pneumonitis, nonspecific interstitial pneumonia, acute and subacute interstitial pneumonia, cryptogenic organizing pneumonia, diffuse alveolar damage, pulmonary fibrosis, alveolar hemorrhage, eosinophilic pneumonia, and pleural effusion (6).

Importantly, acute forms of pulmonary toxicity do not predispose to chronic toxicity (6). Acute forms are more common and may appear within a few hours of the first exposure to the drug, although they generally present after the first week (6). These reactions are usually hypersensitivity reactions and manifest with fever, dyspnea, and cough within hours or weeks of the first dose (7). In contrast, chronic reactions may be cell-mediated or due to direct toxicity (7).

Regarding chronic damage, studies suggest that nitrofurantoin can directly damage normal lung parenchymal cells through oxidative mechanisms, generating an imbalance between oxidants and antioxidants and producing toxic metabolites that cause lung injury and long-term fibrosis (3). Indirect damage, associated with the recruitment of

neutrophils to the lung parenchyma, has also been identified (2).

Although nonspecific interstitial pneumonia is common in chronic reactions, organizing pneumonia, chronic eosinophilic pneumonia, and desquamative interstitial pneumonia have also been identified (7). The type of lung condition that our patient presented was interstitial lung disease (ILD), this is a group of diffuse parenchymal lung diseases with similar clinical, radiographic, physiological and pathological manifestations, characterized by extensive alteration of the alveolar and airway architecture (2).

Risk factors for the development of pulmonary toxicity include renal failure, since the decrease in glomerular filtration rate (GFR) increases drug concentration and the risk of pulmonary toxicity. Although the manufacturer's labeling contraindicates its use in patients with a GFR of 30 to <60 mL/min, and some

While studies suggest it is safe and effective for the short-term treatment of uncomplicated acute cystitis, a retrospective cohort study reported an increased risk of pulmonary adverse events in patients with a glomerular filtration rate <50 mL/min (8).

In a series of 10 cases of nitrofurantoin-associated pulmonary complications, all occurred in women (1). It is estimated that between 85% and 95% of patients who develop pulmonary reactions to this drug are women, likely due to the higher prevalence of urinary tract infections in this population and their prolonged exposure to the drug (1).

The most frequent age of onset is in the sixth and seventh decades of life, with reports of both acute and chronic reactions. However, the chronic form is less common and is more frequently observed in elderly patients (6,7).

In one case series, the median duration of nitrofurantoin treatment before the onset of symptoms was 17 months (1). Chronic pulmonary toxicity is rare and usually occurs in patients who have used the drug for at least six months or more (9). Unlike the acute form, chronic toxicity is not usually preceded by previous acute episodes and can develop after months or even years of continuous treatment (6).

It is important to note that acute lung injury can occur even with small doses, and there does not appear to be a direct relationship between the amount administered (10).

Within the diagnostic approach, the chronic form of pulmonary toxicity develops over weeks or years and is characterized by the presence of a dry cough and progressive dyspnea (9), as was the presentation of our patient. It may also present with nonspecific symptoms such as weight loss and myalgia (6). In some cases, clinical signs such as digital clubbing and inspiratory crepitations may be present (9). Among paraclinical laboratory findings, eosinophilia is a rare finding in these patients, although cases with elevated rheumatoid factor, positive antinuclear antibodies, unrelated to rheumatic diseases (7), and elevated immunoglobulins (6) have been described. Peripheral eosinophilia has been documented primarily in chronic forms of nitrofurantoin

Interstitial Lung Disease Associated with Chronic Nitrofurantoin Use

toxicity (11). However, it was not present in our patient's laboratory findings.

On imaging studies, chest X-ray, the most common finding is the presence of bilateral and basal pulmonary infiltrates in 94% of cases (7).

Computed tomography (CT) changes may include bilateral reticular septal thickening, distortion of pulmonary architecture, honeycombing, and ground-glass opacities (3). High-resolution computed tomography (HRCT) may reveal bilateral ground-glass attenuation, irregular linear opacities, bibasilar air consolidation, and pulmonary fibrosis (7). A characteristic finding in advanced cases is the presence of a "honeycombing" pattern in the lungs (9).

To search for causality with the drug, the Naranjo algorithm, created in 1981, can be used. This is the most widely used algorithm for assessing drug causality in a suspected adverse drug reaction.

The questionnaire consists of nine questions. A score of 9 or higher indicates definite causality, 5-8 indicates probable causality, 1-4 indicates possible causality, and zero indicates negative causality. This algorithm has a sensitivity of 81.2% \pm 5.69% and a specificity of 13.2% \pm 3.56% to predict adverse drug reactions (ADRs) when the categories from "possible" to "definite" are considered positive. (17)

Our patient scored 7 points, placing her in the possible category.

Regarding treatment, in most cases, discontinuation of nitrofurantoin leads to clinical improvement, with or without the use of corticosteroids. However, irreversible pulmonary changes can contribute to long-term morbidity (3).

The primary treatment for IPF consists of eliminating exposure to the triggering antigen. As adjunctive therapy, a limited course of systemic glucocorticoids can be used, depending on the severity. However, some patients develop progressive pulmonary fibrosis (PPF) despite these measures. (12)

It is generally started with oral prednisone; however, in severe hospitalized cases, intravenous pulse methylprednisolone can be used before continuing with oral prednisone. The patient we present presented with signs of severity requiring mechanical ventilation, which is why she was started on pulse methylprednisone. Due to insufficient response, additional immunosuppressive therapy was added. Among the options, azathioprine or mycophenolate mofetil (MMF) was started, the latter being the first. (12,13,18)

Refractory disease is defined as progression despite corticosteroids and immunosuppressants, which was the case in our patient. Treatment options include cyclophosphamide and rituximab, both of which were administered. These have demonstrated efficacy in severe or refractory interstitial disease. (14)

Finally, as part of the approach, patients with interstitial lung disease are at risk of developing progressive pulmonary fibrosis (PPF). This term has been adopted by international respiratory societies to describe non-IPF interstitial lung

disease (interstitial pulmonary fibrosis) with clinical progression. (15)

Diagnostic criteria for PPF are: a decrease in FVC \geq 5% or DLCO \geq 10%, worsening respiratory symptoms, and radiological progression (more fibrosis, traction bronchiectasis, honeycombing, etc.). (15)

Patients with extensive fibrous involvement (\geq 20% of lung volume) are at higher risk of progression.

The antifibrotic treatment of choice is nintedanib. This tyrosine kinase inhibitor blocks multiple pathways involved in the progression of pulmonary fibrosis. The usual dose is 150 mg every 12 hours (max. 300 mg/day). (16)

We must keep in mind that complete remissions are rare (11).

CONCLUSIONS

In Mexico, there is no precise data on the incidence and prevalence of nitrofurantoin-associated pulmonary toxicity, which highlights the importance of reporting cases to more accurately establish the drug association and evaluate possible variations between populations.

It is essential to remember that all medications can cause adverse effects, both acute and chronic. In the case of nitrofurantoin, although it is considered a safe drug, it is crucial to consider its potential adverse effects, especially during long-term treatment.

Although the Naranjo algorithm is the most widely used to assess drug causality and has high sensitivity, its specificity is limited. This suggests the need to develop new scales with better performance in the future. However, we understand that establishing a causal relationship with a drug can be complex, especially in diseases with multifactorial etiologies.

Furthermore, the lack of resources to measure serum drug concentrations in secondary and even tertiary care hospitals makes determining these associations even more difficult. Even when elevated drug levels are detected, the diagnosis of nitrofurantoin pulmonary toxicity remains a diagnosis of exclusion, complicating its clinical management.

To prevent this toxicity, it is recommended that patients on chronic treatment be regularly monitored through clinical evaluations, chest X-rays, and laboratory tests, including liver profiles, to detect potential adverse effects early.

REFERENCES

- I. Queiroz Marcelino, L. ., & Adrian Estrin, M. . (2025). Nitrofurantoin: analysis of its long-term effects and contraindications. *Interamerican Journal of Health Sciences*, 5, 267. <https://doi.org/10.59471/ijhsc2025267>
- II. Akopyan K, Zafar R, Faruqi I. History Is the Key to Diagnosis: A Case of Nitrofurantoin-Induced Interstitial Lung Disease. *Cureus*. 2024 Mar 13; e56097. Available in: <http://dx.doi.org/10.7759/cureus.56097>

Interstitial Lung Disease Associated with Chronic Nitrofurantoin Use

- III. View of Long-term nitrofurantoin induced interstitial lung disease: a case series and literature review. (s. f.). <https://www.mattioli1885journals.com/index.php/sarcoïdosis/article/view/13827/11734>
- IV. SoperUncomplicated Cystitis and Pyelonephritis (UTI). <https://www.idsociety.org/practice-guideline/uncomplicated-cystitis-and-pyelonephritis-uti/>
- V. Maredia, N. N., Fanning, M. J., Christie, A. L., Prokesch, B. C., & Zimmern, P. E. (2020). Adverse effects of chronic nitrofurantoin therapy in women with recurrent urinary tract infections in an outpatient setting. *World Journal Of Urology*, 39(7), 2597-2603. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00345-020-03464-w>
- VI. Gallas, J. M. M., González, Á. O., & Ortiz, J. F. (2015). Toxicidad pulmonar crónica por nitrofurantoína. *Medicina General y de Familia*, 4(3), 85-88. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mgyf.2015.08.004>
- VII. Suliman AM, Alamin MA, Irfan Ul Haq. Nitrofurantoin-Induced Lung Injury: A Reminder of an Overlooked Threat. *Cureus*. 2023 Sep 5;
- VIII. Geerts, A. F. J., Eppenga, W. L., Heerdink, R., Derijks, H. J., Wensing, M. J. P., Egberts, T. C. G., & De Smet, P. A. G. M. (2013). Ineffectiveness and adverse events of nitrofurantoin in women with urinary tract infection and renal impairment in primary care. *European Journal Of Clinical Pharmacology*, 69(9), 1701-1707. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00228-013-1520-x>
- IX. Naureen, S., Hart, S., Jawad, N., Kennan, N., & Faruqi, S. (2023). Long term nitrofurantoin induced interstitial lung disease: a case series and literature review. *PubMed*, 40(4), e2023050. <https://doi.org/10.36141/svld.v40i4.13827>
- X. Chin, A. j., Rashid S., Gharibeh, T. R., Kibbe P. S., Wynbrandt J. H., (2020) Interstitial Lung Disease Secondary to Long-Term Nitrofurantoin Use; e-ISSN 1941- 5923, DOI: 10.12659/AJCR.920386
- XI. Viejo, M. Á. N., Montes, A. F., Montes, J. V., Gómez-Román, J. J., Ibarbia, C. G., & Hernández, J. L. H. (2009). Rapid Resolution of Nitrofurantoin-Induced Interstitial Lung Disease. *Archivos de Bronconeumología*, 45(7), 352-355. [https://doi.org/10.1016/s15792129\(09\)72437-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/s15792129(09)72437-1)
- XII. Flaherty, K. R., Toews, G. B., Lynch, J. P., Kazerooni, E. A., Gross, B. H., Strawderman, R. L., Hariharan, K., Flint, A., & Martinez, F. J. (2001). Steroids in idiopathic pulmonary fibrosis: a prospective assessment of adverse reactions, response to therapy, and survival**Access the “Journal Club” discussion of this paper at <http://www.elsevier.com/locate/ajmselect/>. The American Journal Of Medicine, 110(4), 278-282. [https://doi.org/10.1016/s0002-9343\(00\)00711-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0002-9343(00)00711-7)
- XIII. Um, S. H., Abuzgaia, A., & Rieder, M. (2023). Comparison of the Liverpool Causality Assessment Tool vs. the Naranjo Scale for predicting the likelihood of an adverse drug reaction: A retrospective cohort study. *British Journal Of Clinical Pharmacology*, 89(8), 2407-2412. <https://doi.org/10.1111/bcp.15704>
- XIV. Mankikian, J., Caille, A., Reynaud-Gaubert, M., Agier, M., Bermudez, J., Bonniaud, P., Borie, R., Brillet, P., Cadranel, J., Court-Fortune, I., Crestani, B., Debray, M., Gomez, E., Gondouin, A., Hirschi-Santelmo, S., Israel-Biet, D., Jouneau, S., Juvin, K., Leger, J., . . . Marchand-Adam, S. (2023). Rituximab and mycophenolate mofetil combination in patients with interstitial lung disease (EVER-ILD): a double-blind, randomised, placebo-controlled trial. *European Respiratory Journal*, 61(6), 2202071. <https://doi.org/10.1183/13993003.02071-2022>
- XV. Wells, A. U., & Hirani, N. (2008). Interstitial lung disease guideline. *Thorax*, 63(Supplement 5), v1-v58. <https://doi.org/10.1136/thx.2008.101691>
- XVI. Wells, A. U., Flaherty, K. R., Brown, K. K., Inoue, Y., Devaraj, A., Richeldi, L., Moua, T., Crestani, B., Wuyts, W. A., Stowasser, S., Quaresma, M., Goeldner, R., Schlenker-Herceg, R., Kolb, M., Abe, S., Aburto, M., Acosta, O., Andrews, C., Antin-Ozerkis, D., . . . Ziora, D. (2020). Nintedanib in patients with progressive fibrosing interstitial lung diseases—subgroup analyses by interstitial lung disease diagnosis in the INBUILD trial: a randomised, double-blind, placebo-controlled, parallel-group trial. *The Lancet Respiratory Medicine*, 8(5), 453-460. [https://doi.org/10.1016/s2213-2600\(20\)30036-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/s2213-2600(20)30036-9)
- XVII. Algoritmo de causalidad de Naranjo | Grupo de Farmacología Clínica. (s. f.). <https://clinpharmacolgroup.es/algoritmo-de-causalidad-de-naranjo/>
- XVIII. Kondoh, Y., Taniguchi, H., Yokoi, T., Nishiyama, O., Ohishi, T., Kato, T., Suzuki, K., & Suzuki, R. (2005). Cyclophosphamide and low-dose prednisolone in idiopathic pulmonary fibrosis and fibrosing nonspecific interstitial pneumonia. *European Respiratory Journal*, 25(3), 528-533. <https://doi.org/10.1183/09031936.05.00071004>